

Golden Section for Aerial Base Station Positioning in UAV-assisted Networks

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Abstract—The application of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in improving the coverage of terrestrial networks have been established as an important field in wireless communications. The realization of these systems is dependent on the positioning of the aerial base stations (ABSs) due to their high mobility in three dimensions (3D), which is complicated by the random measurement noise at the receivers. This paper estimates the ABS's position using the golden section (GS) method and compares the throughput gain to terrestrial users served by the ABS, with baseline methods for the same system model. The ABS is associated with users with low downlink throughput from the stationary access point (AP), which is used by default. Additionally, the relationship between the throughput and user density is explored. System throughput of up to 110 Mbps and an average improvement to users' data rate of 125%, are achieved.

Index Terms—Golden section, UAV-assisted networks, UAV placement, UAV positioning, resource allocation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The continually increasing node density in modern and upcoming communication systems, and the diverse use cases that they are applied in, have led to multiple challenges as well as opportunities for the industry's development beyond the Fifth Generation (5G) [1]. These scenarios include enhanced mobile broadband on the ground and in the air through heterogeneous deployments of user-centric heterogeneous networks and UAV-assisted radio access, industrial Internet of Things (IoT), and more. UAVs have been established as a major technological enabler for the implementation of these services as it provides increased coverage, availability and reliability and flexible adaptation [2]. These features make the UAV-based aerial base station (ABS) an important node within the Sixth Generation (6G) heterogeneous network (Het-Net) architecture that combines multiple applications, communication technologies, and types of terminals, which are powered by agile deep learning (DL) methods [3]. In UAV-assisted networks, the APs' service reliability is supported and

extended by the UAV, which is associated to user equipments (UEs) that experience coverage degradation. The authors of [4] explore a variant of this system model with the UAV's trajectory being designed as a Markov decision process to determine the locations over which the ABS will hover for a certain period. Its purpose is to provide wireless charging to stationary IoT UEs, and at the same time, collect data from the terrestrial access point (AP) and the UEs. Network throughput of close to 250 Mbps is achieved. Further, [5] investigates the ABS' positioning and its association to the UEs, such that it increases the minimum network throughput. Through the proposed particle swarm optimization method, gain of close to 11 bps/Hz is reached. The authors of [6] examine an ABS for data harvesting of stationary IoT devices, with the focus of reconstructing the radio environment map and estimating the UAV trajectory that optimizes the downlink data reception in an urban environment. Worst throughput per node of 3 bps/Hz is obtained. Slight improvement in the performance is made by introducing an ABS in a terrestrial vehicular network, which supports the communications of low-throughput users [7]. Further, ABS for emergency communications provision is evaluated in [8] reaching to nearly 70% higher throughput by employing reinforcement learning.

This paper examines the ABS positioning problem when considering the presence of measurement noise that introduces random variations in the received signal strength (RSS), which are unaccounted for in the path loss (PL) model, thus significantly reducing the effectiveness of distance-dependent solutions. A preliminary estimation of the ABS position is estimated using the golden section (GS) method. The results exhibit its effectiveness, when compared to three baseline methods, namely, exhaustive search (ES), maximum sum rate (MSR) and random positioning. The system model assumes the exchange of overhead control messages between the stationary AP and the ABS.

The contribution of this article is summarized as follows:

- ABS positioning estimation based on the GS method to account for the measurement noise in the UEs. The position is determined via a preliminary Monte Carlo simulation, and its efficiency is shown in comparison to three baseline positioning methods. The throughput is

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Fig. 1. UAV-assisted heterogeneous network.

also obtained for different user densities and the results are analyzed. An average improvement to users' throughput of 125% is achieved with the system throughput reaching up to 110 Mbps.

The rest of this paper is organized in this manner. Section II describes the system model and the proposed solution. The results are discussed in Section IV. Finally, the conclusions are given in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This section provides a brief analytical description of the system model that consists of the channel models for the terrestrial (AP-UE) and ground-to-air (i.e. AP-ABS and ABS-UE) links. The system model is presented in Fig. 1, consisting of a stationary AP and N_{UE} UEs, which are associated with it by default, while the ABS associates with the low-throughput UEs. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) $\sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i}$ at the i -th UE with the AP operating on the set \mathcal{W}_i of channels allocated to this UE where $|\mathcal{W}_i| \geq 1$, is represented as:

$$\sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i} = \frac{P_{R,UE}^{\mathcal{W}_i}}{P_0 * \sigma_{NF}}, P_{R,UE}^{\mathcal{W}_i} = (h_t P_{\kappa}^{\mathcal{W}_i} C_{MN}) + P_0, \quad (1)$$

where $P_{\kappa}^{\mathcal{W}_i}$ is the transmission power of either the AP or ABS (denoted as $\kappa \in \{AP; ABS\}$), depending on which of them the UE is associated to. Consequently, the $P_{R,UE}^{\mathcal{W}_i}$ is the received power of the UE, $h_t, t \in \{u; a\}$ is the channel coefficient that describes the path loss (PL), P_0 is the noise power, and $C_{MN} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{NF})$ is the measurement noise coefficient. The latter is a Gaussian variable with a zero mean and variance equal to the receiver's noise figure σ_{NF} . It represents the random fluctuations in the RSS resulting from the imperfect propagation environment and electronic components. The ground-to-air (AP-ABS and ABS-UE) links are characterized by the modified two ray PL model [9], which considers the dominant and surface-reflected components for

UAVs operating on heights H_a lower than 30 m. The channel coefficient h_a (in dB) is described as:

$$h_a = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi}{F_c} \right) - 10\gamma(H_a) \log_{10} \left| \frac{G_l(H_a)}{l} - \frac{G_r(H_a)}{r_1 + r_2} \right|, \\ l = d \sqrt{1 + \frac{(H_T - H_R)^2}{d^2}}, r_1 = \sqrt{H_T^2 + \frac{(d * H_T)^2}{(H_T + H_R)^2}}, \\ r_2 = \sqrt{H_R^2 + \left(d - \frac{d * H_T}{(H_T + H_R)} \right)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where F_c is the central frequency, $d = \sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2 + d_z^2}$ is the three-dimensional distance with d_x , d_y and d_z being the distances between the transmitter and the receiver in the x , y and z axes, H_T and H_R are the heights of the transmitter and the receiver, respectively. The environment is described via the coefficients for direct path $G_l(H_a) = 15$, reflected path $G_r(H_a) = 5$, and height-dependent propagation $\gamma(H_a) = 3.5$. The AP-UE links are characterized by the PL coefficient h_u , which accounts for the distance, multipath fading and shadowing [10]. It is described by the following equation (in dB):

$$h_u = 137.3 + 35.2 * \log_{10}(d). \quad (3)$$

The overall network throughput \mathcal{T} is the sum comprised of the individual capacities \mathcal{T}_{UE_i} of all UEs, which is obtained as:

$$\mathcal{T} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \mathcal{T}_{UE_i} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} |\mathcal{W}_i| \mathcal{B} \log_2(1 + \sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i}), \quad (4)$$

where $|\mathcal{W}_i|$ denote the number of channels allocated to each UE, accordingly, with \mathcal{B} being the bandwidth per channel while overall system bandwidth BW is comprised N_{ch} channels. The set of frequency channels that the ABS operates on is denoted as $\mathcal{F} = \{f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{N_{\mathcal{F}}-1}\}$, while those used by the AP are $\mathcal{G} = \{g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{N_{\mathcal{G}}-1}\}$, where $N_{\mathcal{G}} = \delta_{\mathcal{G}} * N_{ch}$, $N_{\mathcal{F}} + N_{\mathcal{G}} = N_{ch}$, and $\delta_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the portion of channels that are to be allocated to the AP users.

The UEs (denoted as members of the set \mathbb{U} , with $|\mathbb{U}| = N_{UE}$) are placed according to the Matern distribution with density λ_{UE} , which determines their number N_{UE} , and a minimum distance $d_{min,UE}$ between every two UEs. At each consecutive iteration, each UE moves according to the random walk algorithm [10]. These movements, unrestrained in 3D within the terrestrial network area, are performed with a random speed and directed to a randomly selected angle. The UAV flies only within the UAV operational volume, denoted as \mathbb{A} , specified with lengths of S_x^a , S_y^a , and S_z^a in the x , y , and z axes, respectively. The AP is associated to the UEs by default, while those with downlink RSS from the AP below a threshold \mathcal{T}_0 , will attach to the ABS. The UAV operational volume \mathbb{A} is divided into $M_{\mathbb{A}} = M^3$ equidistant locations and it does not intersect with the terrestrial network operational area.

The simulation follows the procedures from the previous work [11]. The positioning of the ABS and UE associations

are updated for every N_s iterations. For the first N_s iterations, all UEs are associated to the AP, while at every update iteration the ABS associates with the UEs that have throughput lower than \mathcal{T}_0 . They form the subset $\mathbb{U}_a \subseteq \mathbb{U}$, such that $\mathbb{U}_a = \{u_i\}, \{i \mid \mathcal{T}_i \geq \mathcal{T}_0\}, i \in \{1, \dots, N_{UE}\}$. The rest of the UEs remain served by the AP. The allocations within the sets of frequency channels for both the ABS and the AP (\mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} , respectively) are retained for the span of each cycle of N_s iterations. At each update iteration, the ABS takes a position described by the coordinates $[s_{x,L}, s_{y,L}, s_{z,L}]$, with $s_{x,L} \in [-\frac{S_x}{2}, \frac{S_x}{2}]$, $s_{y,L} \in [-\frac{S_y}{2}, \frac{S_y}{2}]$, $s_{z,L} \in [-\frac{S_z}{2}, \frac{S_z}{2}]$.

III. GOLDEN SECTION FOR ABS POSITIONING

The goal of this work is to find the positioning location L_{GS} such that it provides coverage over area that is not well-served by the AP, i.e. where the downlink RSS \mathcal{P} from the AP is minimal. This metric is defined as:

$$\mathcal{P} = [h_a(d)P_{AP}C_{MN}] + P_0, \quad (5)$$

where $h_a(d)$ is the PL for the modified two ray model [9], which is dependent on the distance d between the AP and ABS. Considering the random nature of C_{MN} , this is not a trivial function and so the GS method [12] is applied to estimate it. The GS finds the theoretical minimum value of the RSS (5) among all $M_{\mathbb{A}}$ positions in the grid of \mathbb{A} , as a function \mathcal{P} of the d , as it determines the channel coefficient h_a . It should be noted that when applying the GS method for this function, the height of the transmitter H_T is constant because the AP is stationary, while the UAV's height H_R can be neglected because $d \gg H_R$ for more than 90% of the $M_{\mathbb{A}}$ positions in \mathbb{A} . In addition, the distance d_α (corresponding to the ABS position's index α in the grid) at which \mathcal{P} reaches its minimum corresponds to a specific ABS altitude. The GS method evaluates $\mathcal{P}(d)$ in the interval of $[d_{min}; d_{max}]$, which denote the minimum and maximum distances, respectively, between the AP and the ABS. Thus, the GS finds the minimum RSS P_α and consequently, the index $\alpha \in \mathbb{A}$ within the grid, which corresponds to the distance at which P_α is measured. To account for the measurement noise, the GS is applied for a Monte Carlo simulation with 10^5 realizations of C_{MN} . For each d_α , the index α of the distance closest to it (out of \mathbb{A}) is added to the set \mathcal{A}_{GS} . At the end, the theoretical ABS serving position index α_{GS} is obtained as the average of all elements in \mathcal{I}_{GS} .

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This Section outlines the parameters under which the simulations are performed, and also details the findings and their significance. The simulation is run on computer with processor AMD Ryzen 3 PRO 2300U, 8GB of random access memory, solid state drive, and Ubuntu 22.04.5 and Python 3.10. The boundaries of the simulation space are denoted as $[-(S_x/2); (S_x/2)]$ for the x -axis, $[-(S_y/2); (S_y/2)]$ for the y -axis, and $[-(S_z/2); (S_z/2)]$ for the z -axis. The sets of channels are denoted as \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{F} , the system parameters are defined as $\lambda_{UE} = 10$, $N_I = 10^5$ iterations, $N_{ch} = 55$,

$P_{ABS} = P_{AP} = 24$ dBm, $\sigma_{NF} = 9$ dB, $M = 16$, $\mathbb{A} = 4096$, $\delta_G = 0.5$, $N_s = 500$ iterations. The lengths of the simulation environment for both S_x and S_y are 150 m, $S_z = 15$ m, $d_{min} = 11.05$ m and $d_{max} = 106.92$ m. Further, $F_c = 2$ GHz, $B = 180$ kHz, $d_{min,UE} = 0.3$ m and $\mathcal{T}_0 = 5$ Mbps. The AP is positioned at coordinates $[0, 0, 1.5]$ and the UEs are distributed through the Matern method with density of λ_{UE} . The UAV operational space is limited within the axes lengths of S_x , S_y , and $S_z - 5$. To underline the performance gains of the proposed GS method (L_{GS}), they are compared to alternative reference scenarios - random (L_R), exhaustive search (L_{ES}), and maximum sum rate (L_{MSR}) [13] positioning. The cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the throughput averaged over N_s iterations for each method, are illustrated in Fig. 3. These positions are defined through

Fig. 2. CDFs of $\bar{\mathcal{T}}$ for the different positioning cases.

their coordinates as follows. The position L_R denotes a random set of coordinates within \mathbb{A} , while the positions L_{MSR} and L_{ES} are determined through the baseline maximum sum rate (MSR) and exhaustive search (ES) algorithms for each iteration, and the position estimated through GS (L_{GS}) have the following coordinates (corresponding to $s_{x,L}$, $s_{y,L}$ and $s_{z,L}$) $L_{GS} : \{55; -15; 12.67\}$. The results for the MSR method are obtained by executing them for each set of N_{UE} UE locations for the iterations at which there is an update of the ABS position for $N_m = 100$, so that it can estimate that position. Then the acquired ABS positions are applied in the simulation. The reference random and MSR methods differ slightly with the former showing up to 8.7% higher throughput, while the proposed GS positioning outperforms them by up to 15%, delivering up to 110 Mbps. In addition, it provides up to 67% increase for the low-throughput users, which exhibits the method's potency to position the ABS in such a way as to reduce the random variability in the RSS introduced by the measurement noise. When it comes to the ES method, it exhibits the worst performance of up to almost 7% lower throughput than the MSR method. This is result

of the method not accounting for the measurement noise but basing the positioning solely on the smallest distance between the ABS and the UEs. The obtained records for the mean total throughput of the UEs served by the ABS and those served by the AP, has also shown an increase by up to 125%. The better channel conditions in the ABS-UE links have resulted in significant improvement in the service.

Having established the superiority of the GS method, the ABS mean throughput \bar{T} is then evaluated for different UE densities. A considerable improvement is observed with the increase of λ_{UE} even though the number of channels per user declines. This is true for most of the throughput measurements, with up to 6% greater performance for the highest value of λ_{UE} . Nevertheless, due to reduced number of channels, the throughput for CDF over, is almost 20% lower, which means that the highest throughput declines as λ_{UE} increases but the data rate is greater for most of the users.

Fig. 3. CDFs of \bar{T} for different UE densities for the GS positioning location.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work is focused on ABS positioning estimation for a UAV-assisted system model with the presence of measurement noise spurred by the imperfect propagation environment and electronic components inside the receivers. The GS method is applied to find the position which the ABS is to be located at to improve the system throughput. This solution's efficiency is verified against relevant baseline ABS positioning methods and its superiority is established. In addition, the system throughput is assessed for different user densities to further emphasize the GS method's efficiency. These results provide motivation for further development of resource allocation for UAV-assisted networks through methods for user association, power and frequency allocation, and ABS positioning through radio environment maps.

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